

Synthesis and mass spectral studies of copper(II) complexes of 12-membered oxa-azamacrocycles

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Abstract : Cu^{II} complexes of the type [CuLCl₂] (where L = 12-membered macrocycle containing N₂O₂ donor set) have been synthesized by template condensation of 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane with α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione and benzil in the presence of Cu^{II} as a template. These have been characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductances, magnetic moments and IR, electronic and FAB mass spectra.

Keywords : Macrocycles, copper(II), α -diketones.

Cu^{II} complexes of various oxa-aza macrocycles have been synthesized¹, however, those of N₂O₂ macrocycles derived from α -diketones and oxadiazines have not been reported so far. Hence, in continuation of our earlier work on the complexes of azamacrocycles derived from α -diketones² we report herein the synthesis and characterization of Cu^{II} complexes of 12-membered oxa-azamacrocycles derived from α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione or benzil and 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane.

Results and discussion

The reactions of CuCl₂·2H₂O with 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane and different α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione and benzil in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios have resulted in the formation of Cu^{II} complexes of 12-membered oxa-azamacrocyclic (Scheme 1).

The resulting macrocyclic complexes are green solids which are stable at room temperature but decompose at higher temperature (200–225 °C). These are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as methanol, chloroform, acetonitrile and DMF but are soluble in DMSO. The characteristics and analyses of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Molar conductances : The molar conductances of copper(II) complexes are very low (15–25 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹) indicating their non-electrolytic nature (Table 1). Thus the chloro groups appear to be coordinated³.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes.

Infrared spectra : In the IR spectra of Cu^{II} complexes of the macrocycles no absorption bands were observed at 1700 and 3200–3300 cm⁻¹ which could be assigned to free carbonyl and amine groups suggesting that C=O groups have undergone condensation with -NH₂ groups to give C=N linkage, formation of which is further supported by the appearance of strong bands at ~1590 cm⁻¹ due to ν C=N (Table 1)⁴.

Scheme 2. Fragmentation pattern of $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2[12]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_2)\text{Cl}_2]$.

Magnetic moments : The μ_{eff} values of Cu^{II} complexes at room temperature range from 1.85–2.68 B.M. (Table 1) indicating the presence of one unpaired electron. Magnetic moments in the similar range have been reported for Cu^{II} complexes of other macrocycles⁵.

Electronic spectra : The oxa-aza macrocyclic complexes of Cu^{II} exhibit a broad band at $\sim 14590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to ligand field transitions. A band at $\sim 16400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ligand field transitions in copper(II) complexes of 5,7,12,14-tetramethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,5,7,12-tetraene was observed earlier⁶. A broad symmetrical envelope of bands which spans the visible region in copper(II) complexes of 3:4,9:10,17:18,23:24-tetra-benzo-1,12,15,26-tetraaza-5,8,19,22-tetraoxacyclooctacosane has been reported⁵.

The ground state of an octahedrally surrounded Cu^{II} ion is 2E_g . Such complexes⁷ give rise to one absorption band in the visible region near 16000 cm^{-1} . In hexacoordinated complexes of Cu^{II} , regular octahedral geometry is very rare due to Jahn-Teller distortion. The distortion usually leads to

an elongation of two bonds giving four short and two long Cu–L distances.

FAB mass spectra : The FAB mass spectra of four Cu^{II} complexes $[\text{Cu}\{(\text{Me})(\text{Et})[12]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_2\}\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{Cu}\{(\text{Me})(\text{Pr})[12]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_2\}\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{Cu}\{\text{Et}_2[12]\text{-dieneN}_2\text{O}_2\}\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}\{(\text{Me})(\text{Ph})[12]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_2\}\text{Cl}_2]$ have been recorded using NBA matrix. Peaks at m/z 136, 137, 154, 289 and 307 are due to the matrix. All the complexes show peaks corresponding to molecular ions $[\text{M}^+]$ and free macrocycles $[\text{L}^+]$ which confirms the formation of the macrocyclic complexes. In few complexes the peaks due to the $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ or $[\text{L}+\text{H}]^+$ have also been observed⁸. The peak corresponding to the macrocycle in the mass spectra of the complexes of the macrocycles derived from furan-2,5-dialdehyde and 3,6,9-trioxaundecane-1,11-diamine has also been reported⁹. In addition to the peaks due to the molecular ions and the macrocycles, the spectra exhibit peaks assignable to various fragments arising from the thermal cleavage of the macrocycles and their complexes. The fragmentation pattern for the Cu^{II} complex of the macrocycle derived from 3,4-

Table 1. Physical characteristics and analyses of oxazamacrocyclic complexes

Compd.	Colour (yield %)	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Analyses (%) : Found (Calcd.)			μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	IR $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (cm^{-1})
			M	N	Cl			
[Cu{(Me) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }Cl ₂]	Green (32)	215	18.99 (19.09)	8.39 (8.41)	21.03 (21.32)	1.83	27	1580
[Cu{(Me)(Et)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }Cl ₂]	Green (35)	200	18.52 (18.32)	7.98 (8.07)	20.22 (20.45)	1.85	25	1590
[Cu{(Me)(Pr)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }Cl ₂]	Green (68)	225	17.32 (17.61)	7.65 (7.76)	19.72 (19.66)	2.09	24	1585
[Cu{(Et) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }Cl ₂]	Green (40)	210	17.39 (17.61)	7.59 (7.76)	19.32 (19.66)	1.95	23	1593
[Cu{(Me)(Ph)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }Cl ₂]	Green (42)	200	16.23 (16.09)	7.16 (7.09)	17.72 (17.96)	1.80	17	1582
[Cu{(Ph) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }Cl ₂]	Green (68)	220	13.76 (13.90)	6.01 (6.13)	15.31 (15.52)	2.01	15	1598

Table 2. *m/z* values and % relative intensity of important peaks in FAB mass spectra of Cu^{II} complexes of macrocycles

Sl. no.	Compd./ Assignment	I [Cu{(Me)(Et)[12]- dieneN ₂ O ₂ }Cl ₂]	II [Cu{(Me)(Pr)[12]- dieneN ₂ O ₂ }Cl ₂]	III [Cu{(Et) ₂ [12]- dieneN ₂ O ₂ }Cl ₂]	IV [Cu{(Me)(Ph)[12]- dieneN ₂ O ₂ }Cl ₂]
1.	[M] ⁺	345 (3.5)	359 (2.6)	359 (5.2)	393 (5.2)
2.	[M+H] ⁺	346 (7.0)	360 (4.2)	360 (5.2)	394 (10.5)
3.	[M-2Cl] ⁺	275 (10.5)	289 (10.5)	289 (26)	323 (5.2)
4.	[L] ⁺	212 (12.5)	226 (2.6)	226 (5.2)	260 (5.2)
5.	[L+H] ⁺	213 (6.2)	227 (26.3)	227 (18.4)	261 (4.7)
6.	[L-CH ₃] ⁺	197 (9.4)	211 (5.2)	211 (89)	245 (5.2)
7.	[L-CH ₃ -CH ₂] ⁺	183 (7.3)	197 (2.6)	197 (5.2)	-
8.	[L-CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₂] ⁺	-	183 (2.6)	-	-
9.	[L-CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₃] ⁺	168 (21.0)	-	182 (4.7)	-
10.	[L-2(CH ₃ -CH ₂)] ⁺	-	168 (5.2)	168 (10.5)	-
11.	[L-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₅] ⁺	-	-	-	168 (15.7)
12.	[M-2Cl-CH ₃] ⁺	260 (9.4)	274 (2)	274 (4.2)	308 (8.5)
13.	[M-2Cl-CH ₃ -CH ₂] ⁺	246 (42)	260 (3.1)	260 (5.2)	-
14.	[M-2Cl-CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₂] ⁺	-	246 (2.6)	-	-
15.	[M-2Cl-CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₃] ⁺	231 (5.2)	-	245 (4.7)	-
16.	[M-2Cl-2(CH ₃ -CH ₂)] ⁺	-	231 (5.2)	231 (5.2)	-
17.	[M-2Cl-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₅] ⁺	-	-	-	231 (3.10)

hexanedione and 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane is given in Scheme 2. The complex exhibits a molecular ion peak at *m/z* 359 (5.2%) and [M+H]⁺ peak at 360 (5.2%). Fragment **b** is formed due to the loss of two chlorides from molecular ion **a** and appears at *m/z* 289 (26%). There are two possible pathways for the fragmentation of the complex.

(A) In this pathway the metal ion remains attached with the macrocyclic framework and step by step loss of CH₃, CH₂,

CH₃ and CH₂ groups from **b** gives peaks at *m/z* 274 (4.2%), 260 (5.2%), 245 (4.7%) and 231 (5.2%) due to the species **c**, **d**, **e** and **f** respectively. Loss of copper atom from the species **f** finally gives the species **k**.

(B) In this pathway the metal ion may be lost from the macrocycle in the beginning and a peak at *m/z* 226 (5.2%) appears due to the free macrocycle **g**. Subsequent loss of CH₃, CH₂, CH₃ and CH₂ groups from the macrocycle gives peaks

at m/z 211 (89%), 197 (5.2%), 182 (4.7%) and 168 (10.5%) due to the species **h**, **i**, **j** and **k** respectively¹⁰.

Experimental

$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B.D.H.) was of A.R. grade. 1,8-Diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane (Merck), 2,3-pentanedione (Fluka), 2,3-hexanedione (Merck), 3,4-hexanedione (Aldrich), 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione (Aldrich) and benzil (Sisco Chem) were used as supplied and biacetyl (Aldrich), ethanol and DMSO were distilled before use.

Copper was determined volumetrically by sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method and chloride by Mohr's method. Molar conductances of the complexes were determined with the help of Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304 using 10^{-3} M solution in DMSO. IR spectra (KBr) of the samples were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FTIR spectrophotometer in the region 400–4000 cm^{-1} . Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature using Gouy balance at Banasthali Vidyapith, Banasthali (Rajasthan). Electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on a Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes : $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (5.60 mmol, 0.954 g) was dissolved in ethanol (~20 ml) with stirring and 2,3-butanedione (5.60 mmol, 0.482 g in ~15 ml ethanol) was added dropwise. 1,8-Diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane (5.60 mmol, 0.829 g in ~15 ml ethanol) was added with constant stirring. The contents were refluxed for ~14 h. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Similarly, Cu^{II} complexes of other oxa-aza macrocycles derived from 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane and 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione or benzil were synthesized.

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